

STUDY OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN RELATION TO SELF REGULATED LEARNING AND ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Navdeep Kaur¹, Ph.D & Ms. Karmbir Kaur²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Guru Nanak Dev. University, Amritsar

Email: Navdeep.edu@gndu.ac.in

²M.Ed Student, Department of Education, Guru Nanak Dev. University, Amritsar

Email: karmbirkaurgill@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

The purpose of the current study is to examine the effects of self-regulated learning and academic motivation on academic achievement. This study falls under descriptive research design. The sample of this study came from Secondary School Students of Amritsar district. The participants in this study include 200 secondary school students were selected by random sampling. T-test, SD and two-way ANOVA were applied to the analysis of data and the results found that not significant interaction effect of self regulated learning and academic motivation on academic achievement of secondary school students. It found that self regulated learning and academic motivation has not impact on academic achievement because of teacher has not interaction with students, lack of usage of instructional variety during teaching. Teacher not came with proper planning in classroom. So in order to raise the level of self regulated learning and academic motivation, it is recommended that students should take actively participate and co-curricular activities organized by school.

Keywords: Self-Regulated Learning, Academic Motivation, Academic Achievement, Secondary School Students.

[Scholarly Research Journal's](http://www.srjis.com) is licensed Based on a work at www.srjis.com

Introduction

The process of enhancing one's potential and capacity through education and individual and prepare him to be successful member of the society. It means to make once's civilized cultured and progressive in real sense. It helps a person to draw the best out of one's mind and spirit. It

makes a person rational, innovative, constructive, right thinker, intelligent, independent and creator of new values. It is closely links to an individual's life satisfaction and well being.

Academic achievement is the first and lasting duty of a school or some other instructive organization set up by the general public to advance entire academic development and improvement of a kid. Academic achievement assumes a very noteworthy job in the fulfillment of the amicable advancement of the kid. The expectation of academic achievement has accepted colossal significance to its commonsense view. In general, academic achievement is considered as a key basis to pass judgment on one's all out possibilities and limits. It frames the principle premise of affirmation and advancement in a class. It is likewise significant for acquiring a degree or finding a new line of work. For an understudy, estimation of scholastic achievement is significant not just for advanced education on one hand and securing important position on the other, yet in addition for bringing individual fulfillment and social acknowledgment. Academic achievement of secondary school students is thought to be affected by variables including intelligence, readiness, attitude, studying habits, anxiety, health, thinking skills, self-competence, academic motivation, self-regulation learning to name but these few. In this study, academic motivation and academic self-regulated learning have been examined. Today an extremely high academic achievement has become a significant need to look for admission to great courses.

Self-regulated learners are autonomous. As they focus on their studies, so they are able to manage their learning. They plan and study to get the highest possible marks; and use appropriate methods to recall the facts. These abilities finally enable them to be academically high. Self-regulated learners set learning objectives, choose the methods to achieve them, assess their success in reaching those objectives, and then choose and employ novel approaches to improve. Through these processes, they try to manage their own learning efficiently. Self-regulated learners begin with a given task; evaluate the task and set goals according to the information from the evaluation; use strategies to meet the goal; monitor their progress toward the goal and evaluate the use of the strategy; and reinterpretation of the task takes place regarding information attained from internal and external feedback. Self-regulation is a multifaceted concept that includes cognitive, metacognitive, motivational, behavioral, and environmental processes that students might use to improve academic performance. Self-regulation is an umbrella phrase for regulation of the by oneself, oneself. It has to do with

alteration of own responses or internal states. Self-regulation in this context means controlling one's own behaviour. It entails self-regulation of behaviour for a conscious goal. However, one should keep it in mind. some forms of self-regulation may occur without conscious awareness or active involvement of the self. **Academic motivation** is an individual's judgment of his or her capabilities to perform given actions. Motivation can be considered a driving force; a psychological drive that compels or reinforces an action toward a desired goal. Motivation elicits, controls and sustains certain goal-directed behaviors. To be motivated means to be moved to do something. A person who feels no impetus or inspiration to act is thus characterized as unmotivated, whereas someone who is energized or activated toward an end is considered motivated even brief reflections suggest that motivation is hardly a unitary phenomenon. People have not only different amounts, but also different kinds of motivation. That is, they vary not only in level of motivation (i.e. how much motivation), but also in the orientation of that motivation (i.e. what type of motivation). Orientation of motivation concerns the underlying attitudes and goals that give rise to action i.e. it concerns the why of actions. Analysis of the extensive research in this area shows a consistent relationship between motivational factors and achievement and suggests that motivation plays an important role in determining the level of achievement at all stages of academic study. One of the most prominent academic problems that the teachers and parents face is lack of motivation in children toward academic activities. Many school students find themselves in a state in which they do not have the desire to carry out the academic tasks. The absence of academic motivation can lead to feelings of frustration and discontentment. It is important for both parents and teachers to understand why promoting and encouraging academic motivation from an early age is imperative. From the literature review perspectives of study Leblanc et al. (2000) viewed self regulated learning to be an integral segment of the developmental capacity of learning. It is a culture of discovering that urges the understudy to practice their self regulated learning procedures when partaking in an action or when examining or doing school work. It adds to better generally working and remunerating scholastic execution. Self-regulated learning systems are the aggregation of executable plans a student utilizes so as to achieve an objective. These strategies are established in the stages, procedures, and sub-processes of self managed students. The utilization of self-managed learning techniques diminishes the uneasiness and builds self-adequacy, which is legitimately identified

with objective accomplishment and scholastic accomplishment. These constructive outcomes of self-managed system use make it evident their utilization, paying little mind to the space, is useful while taking an interest in the learning procedure. Chaturvedi (2009) investigated the effect of school environment and certain demographic variables on achievement motivation and academic achievement of young adolescents. The sample consisted of 300 students in the age range of 12-15 years, from various schools of Bhopal. Deo-Mohan's achievement motivation scale was used to measure achievement motivation. Percentages of marks obtained by the students in last three years were used as a measure of academic achievement. The results revealed positive significant relationship between academic motivation and achievement. Sanrong et.al. (2019) revealed that self-regulated learning plays an important role in academic achievement. This paper introduces the relationship between self regulated learning and academic achievement. It has been observed that numerous linkages have been made between self-regulated learning and academic success, including being purposeful and goal-oriented and embracing and using a range of strategic behaviours. Additionally, it offers some evidence for the mediation role of academic success in the connection between self-regulated learning and academic progress. The study's conclusions are questioned at the conclusion, and some research is presented on the key areas on which future research should concentrate and how to improve earlier studies. Laur (2017) analyzed empirically the main and interaction effect of academic motivation (high, average and low academic motivation) and locality (rural and urban) on biology achievement among senior secondary school students. Results of the study revealed that the main effects of academic motivation as well as locality were found significantly associated with the academic performance of the students. Further the interaction effect of academic motivation and locality on the achievement was found significant. The study confirms the importance of academic motivation to academic achievement of the students. Thus it can be concluded by making insightful suggestions and recommendations to the authorities, policy makers, schools, teachers, in helping students to enhance their motivation to improve their academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

Study of Academic Achievement in relation to Self-Regulated Learning and Academic Motivation among Secondary School Students.

Delimitations of the problem

The present study was delimited to 200 male and female secondary school students of PSEB of Amritsar city.

Objectives

1. To compare academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to gender.
2. To compare self- regulated learning of secondary school students with respect to gender.
3. To compare academic motivation of secondary school students with respect to gender.
4. To study academic achievement of secondary school students at different levels of self regulated learning.
5. To study academic achievement of secondary school students at different levels of academic motivation.
6. To study the interaction effect of self- regulated learning and academic motivation on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the self-regulated learning of secondary school students with respect to gender.
3. There is no significant difference in the academic motivation secondary school students with respect to gender.
4. There is no significant difference between academic achievement at different levels of self regulated learning on secondary school students.
5. There is no significant difference between academic achievement at different levels of academic motivation of secondary school students.
6. There is no significant interaction effect of self regulated learning and academic motivation at academic achievement of secondary school students.

Methodology

Descriptive survey method was used in study. Data collection was done from secondary school students of Amritsar district, by technique of simple random sampling. The sample consist 200 secondary school students.

Tools

Two psychological tests were used to collect the data; one was Self-Regulated Learning Scale by Gupta and Methani(2007) and Academic Motivation Scale by Dr.T.R. Sharma (2006). Academic Achievement marks of previous class was taken.

Statistical Techniques

The data was analyzed by using t-test, ANOVA was used to analyzed the data.

Results and Discussion

HYPOTHESIS-I

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

TABLE-1 SHOWING THE MEAN,SD AND t VALUE OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

	Gender	N	df	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	Std. Error Difference	t-Value
Academic Achievement	Male	101	198	67.92	8.957	.891	1.240	1.085
	Female	99		66.58	8.563	.861	1.239	

**Not Significant at the 0.05 level.

The Table 1, reveals that there is not significant difference in academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to gender. As shown in table 5.1 the mean score of secondary school male students is 67.92 and that the female students is 66.58 and the value of SD for the two groups was 8.957 and 8.563 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t value of academic achievement of gender is less than the table value 0.05 level. So, our null Hypothesis “*There will be no significant difference in academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to gender,*” was not rejected. It is concluded that male students have higher academic achievement score than female students but the difference is not significant.

HYPOTHESIS-II

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN SELF REGULATED LEARNING OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

TABLE-2 SHOWING THE MEAN, SD AND t VALUE OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

	Gender	N	df	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	Std. Error Difference	t-Value
Self Regulated Learning	Male	101	198	119.515	18.2448	1.8154	2.2740	6.285
	Female	99		105.222	13.5146	1.3583	2.2673	

** Significant at the 0.05 level.

The Table 2, reveals that there is significant difference in self regulated learning of secondary school students with respect to gender. As shown in table 5.2 the mean score of secondary school male students is 119.515 and the female students is 105.222 and the value of SD for the two groups was 18.2448 and 13.5146 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t-value of academic achievement of gender is greater than the table value 0.05 level. So, our null Hypothesis “There will be no significant difference in self regulated learning of secondary school students with respect to gender,” was rejected. It is concluded that male students have higher self regulated learning score than female students but the difference is significant.

HYPOTHESIS-III

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN THE ACADEMIC MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

TABLE-3 SHOWING MEAN,SD AND t VALUE OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

	Gender	N	df	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	Std. Error Difference	t-Value
Academic Motivation	Male	101	198	25.446	5.1913	.5166	.7212	4.774
	Female	99		28.889	5.0039	.5029	.7209	

**Significant at the 0.05 level

The Table 3, reveals that there is significant difference in academic motivation of secondary school students with respect to gender. As shown in table 5.3 the mean of secondary school male students is 25.446 and that the female students is 28.889 and the value of SD for the two groups is 5.1913 and 5.0039 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained t- value of academic achievement of gender is greater than the table value 0.05 level. So, our null Hypothesis “*There will be no significant difference in academic motivation of secondary school students with respect to gender,*” was rejected. It is concluded the female students have higher academic achievement score than male students but the difference is significant.

HYPOTHESIS-IV

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AT DIFFERENT LEVELS OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING

TABLE-4 SHOWING THE MEAN, SD AND ANOVA OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AT DIFFERENT LEVELS OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING

	LEVELS OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING	MEAN	SD	N	Df	F
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	High	65.0000	1.41421	2	199	.560
	Average	67.4915	8.82540	177		
	Low	65.4762	8.66960	21		
	Total	67.2550	8.76837	200		

** Not significant at the 0.05 level

From table 4, it can be seen that F value for the interaction effect levels of self regulated learning at academic achievement of secondary school students came out to be .560, which is not significant at 0.05 level. It indicates that levels of self regulated learning have no effect on academic achievement of secondary school students. So, our null hypothesis, “*There is no significant difference between academic achievement at different levels of self regulated learning of secondary school students*” was not rejected. It is further concluded that average students have higher self-regulated learning score.

HYPOTHESIS-V

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AT DIFFERENT LEVELS OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION

TABLE-5 SHOWING THE MEAN, SD AND ANOVA OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AT DIFFERENT LEVELS OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION

	LEVELS OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION	MEAN	SD	N	Df	F
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	High Academic Motivation	66.5652	7.95913	23		
	Average Academic Motivation	67.5149	8.71391	101		
	Low Academic Motivation	67.1184	9.16074	76	199	.124
	Total	67.2550	8.76837	200		

** Not Significant at the 0.05 level

From table 5, it can be seen that F value for the interaction effect levels of academic motivation at academic achievement of secondary school students came out to be .124, which is not significant at 0.05 level. It indicates that levels of academic motivation not effect on academic achievement of secondary school students. So, our null hypothesis, “*There is no significant difference between academic achievement at different levels of academic motivation of secondary school students*” is not rejected. It is further concluded that average students have higher academic motivation score.

HYPOTHESIS-VI

THERE IS NOSIGNIFICANT INTERACTION EFFECT OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING AND ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

TABLE-6SHOWING THE TWO WAY ANOVA OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING AND ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

DEPENDENT VARIABLE	SOURCE	SUM OF SQUARES	df	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	LEVEL OF SELF REGULATED LEARNING(A)	119.155	4	29.789	.378	.824
	LEVEL OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION(B)	43.452	2	21.726	.276	.759
	SELF REGULATED LEARNING* ACADEMIC MOTIVATION(A*B)	371.559	6	61.927	.785	.582
	ERROR	14743.009	187	78.840		

Self-regulated learning (A)

It is seen from the table that the F-ratio for the difference between the academic motivation and self regulated learning is .378 which in comparison to the table value is found to be not significant at 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that the effect of academic achievement is not to be found on the self-regulated learning.

Academic motivation (B)

It is seen from the table that F-ratio for the difference between the academic achievement and academic motivation is .276 which in comparison to the table value is found to be not significant at 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that the effect of academic achievement is not to be found on academic motivation.

Interaction between Self-regulated learning and Academic motivation (A*B)

It may be seen from the table that F-ratio for the interaction between academic motivation and self regulated learning is .785 which is comparison to the table value was found to be not significant at 0.05 level of significance. This suggested that interaction effect of academic achievement is not to be found on self regulated learning and academic motivation. Hence, our null hypothesis “there is not significant interaction effect of self regulated learning and academic motivation of secondary school students” is not rejected.

Conclusion

The present study sought to explore the effect of Self Regulated Learning and Academic Motivation on Academic Achievement. Study revealed that Self Regulated Learning and Academic Motivation no effect on Academic Achievement. In order to raise the level of Self Regulated Learning and Academic Motivation, it is recommended that students should take actively participate in academic and co-curricular activities organized by school.

Educational implications

1. The present study reveals males' students have higher academic achievement score than female. To improve the academic achievement school management should be aware about the need of the time and should include those strategies for the student especially female students which can increase academic achievement.
2. The present study reveals male have higher self regulated learning score than female. To improve the self regulated learning school management should be aware about the need of the time and should include strategies (such as promote reflective dialogue, provide corrective feedback, help learner to link new experience to prior learning) for the students especially female students which can increase the level of self regulation among them so they may become more self regulated

3. The present study reveals female has higher academic motivation score than male. To improve the motivation teachers should also show right direction to students. Teacher should guide and enhancing their learning pattern and study habits.
4. The present study reveals that not significant difference was found between academic achievement and self regulated learning. To improve the self regulated learning teacher should aware the need of time and strategies for the students. . Self-regulation is particularly important in helping students activate and maintain cognitive, behavioral, and affective processes that are consistently geared towards achieving goals. SRL skills play an important role in organizing learning processes, practicing self-discipline, developing good habits and making more effective and successful. The skill should be taught to every student in school.

References

- Adepoju, T.L. (2008). *Motivational Variables and Academic Performance of Urban and Rural Secondary School Students in Nigeria*. *KEDI Journal of Educatio Policy*, 5 (2), 23- 39.
- Ahmad, I., & Rana, S. (2012). *Affectivity, Achievement Motivation, and Academic Performance in College Students*, *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 27(1), 107-120.
- Ahmed, J. (1998). *Achievement Motivation Differences among Adolescent Boys and Girls of Various Ordinal Birth Position*. *Indian Psychological Review*, 50(1), 1-5.
- Akhter, A., & Pandey, S. (2018). *A study of parental encouragement on the academic achievement of secondary level students in J & K*. *International Journal of Advanced Educational Research*, 3(2), 500-503.
- Alam, M.J.F., (2017). *Relation between Academic Anxiety and Academic Achievement among school students of Murshidabad District*. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 3(3), 3354-3357.
- Alotaibi, K., Tohmaz, R., Jabak, O. (2017). *The relationship between self-regulated learning and academic achievement for a sample of community college students sat King Saud University*. *Education Journal*, 6(1), 28-37.
- Broussard, S.C. (2002). *The Relationship Between Classroom Motivation And Academic Achievement In First and Third Graders*. A Thesis Submitted to the Graduate Faculty of the Louisiana State University. <http://etd.lsu.edu/>
- Chaturvedi, M. (2009). *School Environment, Achievement Motivation and Academic Achievement*. *Indian Journal of Social Science Researches*, 6, 2, 29- 37.

- Chen, C.S. (2002). *Self-regulated learning strategies and achievement in an introduction to information systems course*. *Information Technology, Learning, and Performance Journal*, 20(1), 11-25.
- Cheng, E.C.K. (2011). *The role of self-regulated learning in enhancing learning performance*. *The International Journal of Research and Review*, 6 (1), 1-16.
- Chowdhury, M.S., & Shahabuddin (2007). *Self-Efficacy, Motivation and their Relationship to Academic Performance of Bangladesh College Students*. *College Quarterly*, 10(1).
- Clarebout, G., Horz, H., & Schnotz, W. (2010). *The relations between self-regulation and the embedding of support in learning environments*. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 58(5), 573-587.
- Cleary, J.T. and Plattern, P. (2013). *Examining the correspondence between self regulated learning and academic achievement: A case study analysis*. *Educational Research International*, 2013(1), 1-18.
- Dent, A.L. (2013). *The relationship between self-regulation and academic achievement: A meta-analysis exploring variation in the way constructs are labeled, defined and measured* (Ph.D. dissertation, Duke University, North Carolina). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10161/7265>.
- Elstad, E., & Turmo, A. (2010). *Students' self-regulation and teacher's influence in science: Interplay between ethnicity and gender*. *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 28 (3), 249-260.
- Fauzi, A. and Widjajanti, D.B. (2018). *Self-regulated learning: the effect on student's mathematics achievement*. *IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* 1097. 012139 doi :10.1088/1742-6596/1097/1/012139.
- Francis, Anand, Attia G., R. Haver-Dieter, Adam D. K., Katie K., Allison L.M. Kirk, Stanley L., Arul M. T., & Teresa Ye (2004). *Promoting Academic Achievement and Motivation*. Thesis submitted in University of Maryland. www.gemstone.umd.edu
- Ghazi, Safdar R., Riasat, A., Saqib, S. and Hukamdad, H. (2010). *Parental Involvement in Children Academic Motivation*. *Asian Social Science*, 6(4).
- Ginsburg, G.S., & Bronstein, P. (1993) *Family Factors Related to Children's Intrinsic/Extrinsic Motivational Orientation and Academic Performance*. *Child Development*, 64, 1461-1474.
- Graham, S. & Harris, K. R. (2000). *The role of self-regulation and transcription skills in writing and writing development*. *Educational Psychologist*, 35(1), 3-12.
- Guay, et.al., (2010). *Intrinsic, identified, and controlled types of motivation for school subjects in young elementary school children*. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80(4), 711-735.
- Gyanani, T.C. 1999 *Self-concept of the adolescents in relation to caste, religion and gender difference*, *prachi Journal of psychocultural dimension* Vol.15(1) 29-36.

- Halloran, R.K. (2011). *Self-regulation, executive function, working memory and academic achievement of female high school students* (Ph.D. Dissertation, Fordham University, New York). Retrieved from <http://fordham.bepress.com/dissertations/AAI3452791/>.
- Harris, K.R., Friedlander, B.D., Saddler, B., Frizzelle, R., & Graham, S. (2005). *Self-monitoring of attention versus self-monitoring of academic performance: Effects among students with ADHD in the general education classroom*. *Journal of Special Education*, 39 (3), 145-156.
- Hudesman, G., Millet, S. and Niezgodá, B. (2013). *The use of self-regulated learning, formative assessment, and mastery learning to assist students enrolled in developmental Mathematics: A demonstration project*. *The International Journal of Research and Review*, 10, 1-17.
- Inan, B. (2013). *The relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and academic in a Turkish EFL setting*. *Academic Journal: Educational Research and Reviews*, 18(17), 1544-1550.
- Kim, EunJoo, Kim, Joohan, & Hong, Sehee (2007). *The Effects of Students' Intrinsic Motivation on Academic Achievement and Preference for Cooperative*. Paper Presented at the Annual Meeting of the International Communication Association.
- Kolovelonis, A., Goudas, M., & Dermitzaki, I. (2011). *The effect of different goals and self-recording on self-regulation of learning a motor skill in a physical education setting*. *Learning and Instruction*, 21 (3), 355-364.
- Kosnin, A.M. (2007). *Self-regulated learning and academic achievement in Malaysian undergraduates*. *International Education Journal*, 8 (1), 221-228.
- Kumar, A., & Yadav, D. (2015). *A comparative study of academic achievement motivation of senior secondary students*. *Bhartiyam International Journal of Education & Research*, 4(3), 33-39.
- Kumari, Sushma. (2001). *A study of adolescent pupil attitudes towards gender roles in relation to development of self-concept and social awareness*. Ph.d. Edu., kota open university. Guide Dr. M.K.Gupta.Patel, M.R.1996 *The progress of Education*, Vol. LXX1 (4) 74-76. *Study habits of pupil and its impact upon their Academic Achievement*.
- Labuhn, A.S., Zimmerman, B.J., & Hasselhorn, M. (2010). *Enhancing students' self-regulation and mathematics performance: The influence of feedback and self-evaluative standards*. *Metacognition and Learning*, 5 (2), 173-194.
- Levesque, C., Zuehlke, A. N., Stanek, L. R., & Ryan, R. M.(2004). *Autonomy and competence in German and American university students: A comparative study based on self-determination theory*. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96, 68-84.
- Muola, J. M. (2010) *A Study of the Relationship Between Achievement Motivation and Home Environment Among Standard Eight Pupils*. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 5(5), 213- 217.

- Pelt, J. (2008). *The relationship between self-regulated learning and academic achievement in middle school students: A cross-cultural perspective* (Unpublished D.Ed. dissertaiom. University of South Carolina, Columbia.
- Pintrich, P. R., & Zusho, A. (2002). *The development of academic self -regulation: The role of cognitive and motivational factors*. In A. Wigfield & J. Eccles(Eds.), *Development of achievement motivation* (pp.249–284). San Diego, CA:Academic Press.
- Radovan, M. (2011). *The relation between distance students' motivation, their use of learning strategies and academic success*. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 10(1), 217-222.
- Sahranavard, S., Miri M. R., Salehiniya H. (2018). *The relationship between selfregulation and educational performance in students*. *J Edu Health Promot [serial online]* 2018 [cited 2019 Dec 3];7:154. Available from: <http://www.jehp.net/text.asp?2018/7/1/154/248932>
- Sanrong et.al. (2019). *The Relationships of Self-regulated Learning and Academic Achievement in University Students*. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 60, 01003. https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20196001003_PHECSS2018
- Valle, A., Nunez, J.C., Cabanach, R.G., Gonzalez-Pienda, J.A., Rodriguez, S., Rosario,P., Cerezo, R. and Mumoz-Cadavid, M.A. (2008). *Self-regulated profiles and academic achievement*. *Psicothema*, 20(4), 724-731.
- Vallerand, R. J., & Ratelle, C. F. (2002). *Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation: A hierarchical model*. In E. L. Deci & R. M. Ryan (Eds.), *The motivation and self-determination of behaviour: Theoretical and applied issues* (pp. 37–63). Rochester, NY:University of Rochester Press.
- Zhang, H. and Huang, R. (2010). *Learning in CALL environment: An exploration of selfregulated learning constructs on Chinese students' academic performance*. In: *Hybrid learning: Third International Conference, ICHL Beijing, China, August 2010.Proceedings*. Edited by P.Tsang, S.K.S.Cheung, V.S.K. Lee and R. Huang. BerlinHeidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 370-382.
- Zimmerman, B.J., Martinez-Pons, M. (1986). *Development of a structural interview for assessing student use of self-regulated learning strategies*. *American Educational Research*, 23(4), 614-628.
- Zimmerman, B.J., Martinez-Pons, M. (1988). *Construct validation of a strategy model of student self-regulated learning*. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 80(3), 284 290.
- Zimmerman, B.J. (2000). *Attaining self-regulation: A social cognitive perspective*. In M. Boekaerts, P.R. Pintrich, & M. Zeidner (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulationresearch and applications* (pp. 13–39). San Diego, California: Academic Press.

Zimmerman, B.J. (2004). *Socio-cultural influence and students' development of academic self-regulation: A social-cognitive perspective*. In D.M. McInerney & S. V. Etten (Eds.), *Big theories revisited* (pp.139-164). Greenwich, CT:Information Age.

Zimmerman, B. (2008). *Investigating self-regulation and motivation: Historical background, methodological developments, and future prospects*. *American Educational Research Journal*, 45(1), 166-183.